

Funded by
the European Union

CLASSICA

Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery

D6.1 Website and Online Communications Setup Report

Document date: 1 August 2022

Document version: 1.3

Deliverable No: D6.1

Dissemination Level: Public

Full Name	Short Name	Beneficiary Number	Role
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	UCD	1	Coordinator
INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE CONTRE LES CANCERS DE L'APPAREIL DIGESTIF	IRCAD	2	Beneficiary
STICHTING E.A.E.S	EAES	3	Beneficiary
PINTAIL LTD	PT	4	Beneficiary
KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	UCPH	5	Beneficiary
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO	UNITO	6	Beneficiary
ZIEKENHUIS OOST-LIMBURG AUTONOME VERZORGINGSINSTELLING	ZOL	7	Beneficiary
ARCTUR RACUNALNISKI INZENIRING DOO	ARCTUR	8	Beneficiary
STICHTING VUMC	VUMC	9	Beneficiary
THE PENNSYLVANIA STATE UNIVERSITY	PSU	10	Beneficiary
KONVENT DER BARMHERZIGEN BRUDER GRAZ	BBGRAZ	11	Beneficiary

D6.1 Website and Online Communications Setup Report

Executive Summary

D6.1 'Website and Online Communications Setup Report' describes the CLASSICA project website, which went live in the opening months of the project and the social media channels that were set up simultaneously.

CLASSICA's work package (WP)6, 'Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation', has three communication and dissemination objectives:

- Communicate and disseminate the project, its value, benefits, and results to specific target audiences, using tailored messages and selected channels for each audience, including: the public and media, surgeons and cancer patients, healthcare agencies and payors.
- Stimulate further research and development by other teams, building on our work.
- Create awareness of and demand for the novel results of the project, including promoting our technologies and results to potential commercial partners.

This deliverable is an output of Task 6.1 'Website and Online Communications', and describes the project website and social media channels. Communication activities for the project focus on sharing the project itself and regular updates will be shared throughout the lifetime of the project. This is the first deliverable from WP6.

The purpose of the CLASSICA website is to serve as a hub for project communication and dissemination. One of the first steps in publicly communicating the project is the establishment and maintenance of the project website, with descriptions of the project objectives, team involvement, key innovations, and societal impact.

Developed in collaboration with the project partners and in accordance with our Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP, D6.2), the website has been designed with a range of audiences in mind. Key target audiences for Task 6.1 include the general public and media, the medical community, research communities and key opinion leaders. The website's tone is serious and engaging. It is accessible to the general public interested in new technological developments in AI and cancer, and more knowledgeable audiences with specific expertise or special interests in the project domains. The website is optimised for mobile browsing and future multilingual translation.

This deliverable provides an overview of the project website, a description of the web design process, technology stack, website pages and features, as well as Twitter and LinkedIn social media accounts. The website and social media channels will be updated throughout the project's lifetime, with updates reported in the Periodic Reports.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
Table of Contents.....	2
List of Figures.....	3
List of acronyms, definitions and abbreviations.....	3
1 Introduction.....	4
1.1 Introduction to CLASSICA	4
1.2 Website and Online Communication Activities	4
2 Online Communication - Approach.....	5
2.1 CLASSICA online communication	5
2.2 Project logo	5
2.3 Target audiences	6
2.4 Process for online development	6
2.4.1 Overview.....	6
2.4.2 Technology	7
3 Results.....	8
3.1 CLASSICA website	8
3.1.1 Design decisions	8
3.1.2 Home page	9
3.1.3 Project	10
3.1.4 Media & Materials.....	11
3.1.5 Project Publications.....	12
3.1.6 Related projects.....	13
3.1.7 Team	14
3.1.8 Partner Profile	15
3.1.9 News	16
3.1.10 Contact	17
3.2 CLASSICA Twitter	18
3.3 CLASSICA LinkedIn	18
4 Impact & Conclusion	19

List of Figures

Figure 1 CLASSICA logo.....	5
Figure 2 CLASSICA typography in Quicksand font via an open-source license	6
Figure 3 CLASSICA colour pallet.....	6
Figure 4 CLASSICA homepage animated banner	8
Figure 5 CLASSICA homepage.....	9
Figure 6 Project page.....	10
Figure 6 Media & Materials page	11
Figure 6 Project Publications page	12
Figure 6 Related Projects page	13
Figure 6 Team page	14
Figure 6 UCD - the Mater Partner Profile page	15
Figure 6 News page	16
Figure 6 Contact page.....	17
Figure 6 CLASSICA on Twitter @classicaproject.....	18
Figure 6 CLASSICA on LinkedIn – CLASSICA Horizon Europe	19

List of acronyms, definitions and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CMS	Content Management System
DoA	Description of Action
DTIF	Disruptive Technologies Innovation Fund
EU	European Union
IP	Intellectual Property
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction to CLASSICA

The Horizon Europe CLASSICA project will deliver and clinically validate an AI-based decision support technology, which allows rapid identification of the presence and distribution of cancer tumours. Validation will be carried out across several clinics, surgical teams, and countries.

Cancer and healthy tissue have radically different local blood perfusion patterns. This perfusion can be captured using near-infrared video after systemic fluorophore (indocyanine green) injection. Analysis of the video can digitally identify regions of cancer by tracking the perfusion over the initial seconds after dye administration by comparing the fluorescence signal in these areas with those in adjacent normal tissue within the same endolaparoscopic field of view. Application of AI methods (including computer vision and machine learning techniques) has enabled this differential classification to occur in real time so that better, individualised surgical decisions can be taken during an operation

The CLASSICA AI-based technology will assist surgeons in real time during operations by accurately identifying cancerous versus healthy tissue. During the operation, a smart camera captures the colour changes in tissue after the administration of a safe fluorescent dye. Video is processed by the AI, helping the surgeon to define excision extent. This added support, combined with the surgeon's judgement and expertise, will minimise post-surgery complications and reduce the risk of cancer recurrence in the patient.

The specific objectives of the project are to:

- Deploy and carry out clinical validation studies across five clinical settings, including Ireland, Belgium, Austria, Italy, and the Netherlands.
- Assess the usability, safety, and performance of the CLASSICA system.
- Agree on standard operating protocols for the implementation and use of the CLASSICA system.
- Develop and deliver training for the use of CLASSICA tissue classification tools during biopsy and surgery.
- Develop new guidelines to help guide the use of AI for surgical decision support.

The project builds on breakthrough research by the Irish DTIF Consortium comprising UCD, RCSI and IBM Research over the last three years at the Mater Hospital regarding the use of special dyes and AI to improve outcomes in cancer surgery.

1.2 Website and Online Communication Activities

The CLASSICA website is live at <https://classicaproject.eu/>. This document presents a brief overview of the project website and supplements the website itself. It includes a description of the web design process (domain, pages, materials for different audiences, etc.) that has been carried out under Task 6.1. The website and online communication activities are organised and managed under WP6 of the DoA, led by PT and UCD. All partners in the Consortium play an important role in WP6 by providing essential content and feedback, reporting on project outputs from their WPs, and by taking advantage of their existing networks to promote the project and our online communication channels.

2 Online Communication - Approach

2.1 CLASSICA online communication

An online presence is a critical component of CLASSICA. Our website will provide a hub to host all our communication and dissemination outputs and promote our project activities. It will also promote our research results, thereby widening exploitation opportunities. Establishing and developing an online profile is a continuous process and cannot be taken for granted. By telling our story and sharing knowledge, skills and data, we will publicly establish the project as a prime mover in the space of AI decision-support for the identification of the presence and distribution of cancer tumours.

Due diligence will be carried out prior to publishing our outputs (web pages, news items, social media) or disseminating our results (scientific magazines, scientific articles, databases) to ensure that IP and potential publications are protected.

2.2 Project logo

The CLASSICA logo (Figure 1), logo text element (Figure 2), colour palette (Figure 3), and communication plan for public-facing media (c.f. CDP, D6.2) were developed in the early months of the project so that the design of the website reflected the brand of CLASSICA.

The CLASSICA logo is shown in Figure 1. Several iterations of the logo were created before a final selection was made. The logo and brand development process and guidelines for use are discussed in some depth in D6.2 'Communication and Dissemination Plan'. The logo is used for all CLASSICA dissemination activities. Multiple versions of the logo are available to the team – from low resolution to high resolution, and for digital and print.

Figure 1 CLASSICA logo

CLASSICA

Figure 2 CLASSICA typography in Quicksand font via an open-source license

Figure 3 CLASSICA colour pallet

The project brand identity includes the logo, typography, colour scheme, tagline, fonts used, tone of voice, as well as positioning. These are discussed in some depth in deliverable D6.2.

2.3 Target audiences

Our website and social media accounts will serve as a gateway to the broader community and general public, by sharing project results and making the science and technology accessible to non-scientific audiences. The main target audiences for online communications are the public and media, surgeons and cancer patients, healthcare agencies and payors. Our plan for communication activities is outlined in our CDP (deliverable D6.2).

2.4 Process for online development

2.4.1 Overview

The project website was developed in collaboration with all project partners. The initial website includes:

- Homepage with project overview (project goals, concept, background),
- Project overview (objectives, background science and technology, details of the implementation study)
 - Project media and materials
 - Project publications, including publications prior to CLASSICA,
 - Related projects
- Team profiles
 - and individual pages for each partner
- News feed that is updated regularly
- Contact functionality

PT is responsible for regularly updating the website content and maintaining the social media channels. Partners will regularly be asked to provide content for the website, in particular for project news as well as for relevant related news where a project partner is involved. For example, this may include

events, interviews, invited talks at relevant conferences, publication news, etc. PT will also provide design support for any extensions to the website (e.g., the addition of new features, pages, etc.).

Content published on the website will typically be tailored for the general public. Additional material targeting our specialist audiences (surgeons, scientists and researchers, healthcare buyers and hospital administrators, and potential collaborators) will also be made available. Communication via the website and over social media will use the project 'tone of voice' – it will be simple, relevant, and useful. Content will be reinforced with evidence and will be illustrated with supporting images or other media. Technical and scientific information will be made accessible by translating it into a language that is simple to understand. Essentially, the content will be tailored to suit different audiences whilst ensuring that all audience types understand our core message.

The project website is live at <https://classicaproject.eu/>. The EU domain (.eu) was registered to give us a European identity and signify that this is a pan-European collaborative project.

In addition, Twitter and LinkedIn accounts were launched, and they include components of the CLASSICA logo and colour scheme.

2.4.2 Technology

The project website uses WordPress¹, an open-source content-management system (CMS). Around one-third of websites use this system, which has enabled us to implement a project-specific theme that works on a multitude of platforms and devices (across multiple browsers and on devices such as desktops and mobiles). WordPress is an industry-standard and is easy to use, meaning that new pages, news posts, and other media can be developed rapidly, all the while conforming to the website theme and working responsively. In addition, WordPress is supported by a wealth of plugins to facilitate better functionality and usability. For example, the website technology will facilitate future multilingual translation. Regular automatic back-ups of the website and associated database ensure that the website has good fault tolerance, availability, and can roll back to previous versions where necessary.

Google Analytics² enables us to monitor and track our visitors. This important tool enables us to assess the impact of news articles, the number of visitors to the website, their locations, and the platforms they are on. Understanding our visitors, their behaviours, and where they come from means that we can understand how effective our online communication is.

¹ <https://wordpress.org/>

² <https://analytics.google.com/>

3 Results

3.1 CLASSICA website

3.1.1 Design decisions

The website theme includes some consistent elements that are visible throughout. In particular, this includes the use of the project colour scheme, consistent typography, as well as a common header and footer that are visible across all pages.

Figure 4 CLASSICA homepage animated banner

Logo and colour pallet: The CLASSICA logo features at the top left of each page. The colour scheme used on the homepage animation and throughout the site draws from our colour palette.

Header: A site menu is held in the header and is consistent across all pages. A sticky header provides navigation links when the user scrolls. Links to our social media channels are also present.

Footer: Horizon Europe acknowledgements and project information are contained in the footer alongside recent tweets. The footer is consistent across all pages.

The following illustrates the main pages developed at the start of the project. These pages will be updated and new pages added throughout the project's lifetime.

3.1.2 Home page

The CLASSICA homepage features a brief overview of the project goals, including the project mission, the clinical trial, collaboration and the expertise that partners bring to the project, the importance of communication, and the background AI technology for fluorescence analysis.

Figure 5 CLASSICA homepage

3.1.3 Project

The Project page provides an overview of the project, the problem domain, and project objectives.

CLASSICA

HOME PROJECT TEAM NEWS CONTACT

About CLASSICA

Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery

What is CLASSICA?

CLASSICA is an EU-funded project looking at how to deploy cancer classification AI technology in the operating theatre. We will clinically validate a novel AI-guided intraoperative decision-support technology across several clinics, surgical teams, and countries. Our technology will differentiate between cancerous and non-cancerous tissues in real-time.

Colorectal cancer is the third most common cancer type globally and the second most common cause of cancer death, leading to almost one million deaths annually. In CLASSICA, we transform a research prototype for classifying colorectal cancer tissue into a tool that will be used by surgeons in the operating theatre. The aim of the technology is to deliver decision-making support for cancer surgeons across Europe. We will:

- » Further develop, test, and launch the CLASSICA platform and use it in **five leading cancer surgery centres across Europe**, including Ireland, Belgium, Austria, Italy, and the Netherlands. Cancer classification information will be made available to the surgeons and provide valuable support for critical clinical decisions.
- » Deploy CLASSICA as part of a **multi-country implementation study involving 500 patients**, looking at improved clinical outcomes, classification accuracy, surgeon satisfaction with the digital tool, and much more.
- » Optimise the classification technology for **generalisability across clinics**. While the AI technology has been tested successfully at two hospitals in Ireland, it is typical in surgery to encounter significant variation in the successful use of new techniques and technologies.
- » **Validate biopsy and tumour identification across a heterogeneous population** of patients.

Optimised resection of large rectal polyps is a key area of current surgical practice where the

Figure 6 Project page

3.1.4 Media & Materials

The Media & Materials page provides an overview of the project details and links to project materials. Initially, this includes the project press releases and project logo. Over time, this page will host other dissemination materials such as flyers, videos, and other project assets.

Figure 7 Media & Materials page

3.1.5 Project Publications

The Project Publications page will host the publications that are output by the project. This will include the publication details, a link to download the full publication, the abstract, and a lay summary of the publication. Additionally, this page currently lists some of the key publications that underlie the CLASSICA project. This work was not supported by CLASSICA but provided a foundation for significant parts of the project.

Figure 8 Project Publications page

3.1.6 Related projects

The Related Projects page links to other projects that are related to CLASSICA. This page will be updated over time to include other projects the team is involved in and projects funded under the same Horizon Europe topic (HORIZON-HLTH-2021-DISEASE-04-04).

The screenshot shows the 'Related Projects' page of the CLASSICA website. The page has a white background with a red header bar. The CLASSICA logo is in the top left, and the navigation menu includes 'HOME', 'PROJECT' (highlighted), 'TEAM', 'NEWS', and 'CONTACT'. The main content area is titled 'Related Projects' and features three project cards:

- COLOSSUS**: Advancing a Precision Medicine Paradigm in metastatic Colorectal Cancer: Systems based patient stratification solutions. Description: COLOSSUS is an EU-funded H2020 project that aims to provide new and more effective ways to classify patients with a specific subtype of metastatic colorectal cancer (microsatellite stable RAS mutant metastatic colorectal cancer or MSS RAS mt mCRC) and to develop new treatment options for them. The ultimate goal is to deliver a personalised medicine approach for patients with MSS RAS mt mCRC, which is currently not available.
- PORSAV**: Protecting OR Staff from Aerosolized Virus. Description: PORSAV is an innovation action project funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme as part of Europe's urgent response to the COVID-19 pandemic. The project takes a novel technology for surgical safety from the prototype stage to mass production and distribution.
- QUSTom**: Quantitative Ultrasound Stochastic Tomography.

Figure 9 Related Projects page

3.1.7 Team

The Team page provides an overview of the project partners, with links to each partner's profile. The project involves 11 partners from 9 countries across the globe with expertise in colorectal cancer, precision surgery, AI and technology, biomedical law and ethics, surgical training, and surgical guidelines.

Figure 10 Team page

3.1.8 Partner Profile

Each partner organisation is represented, with their role in the project and relevant expertise outlined. The partner profile for the UCD Centre for Precision Surgery at the Mater is illustrated in Figure 11 below.

Figure 11 UCD - the Mater Partner Profile page

3.1.9 News

The News page will share project news and updates, including press releases, conferences, project meetings and other activities. News items will be shared on the project's social media channels and via partners' social media accounts, helping drive traffic to the website.

Figure 12 News page

3.1.10 Contact

The Contact page enables users to get in touch with the project team. Google's reCAPTCHA functionality protects this page. The submission form is managed by PT, with messages directed to the Coordinator and the wider team after review.

The screenshot shows the 'Contact Us' page for the CLASSICA project. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the CLASSICA logo on the left and links for HOME, PROJECT, TEAM, NEWS, and CONTACT on the right. The main heading is 'Contact Us' with the subtext 'Get in touch with our team' and an illustration of two people talking. Below this is a 'Get in touch' section with a contact form. The form includes fields for Name, Email, Subject, and a large text area for 'Your Message'. There is also a checkbox for 'Agree to terms' and a 'SEND' button at the bottom.

Figure 13 Contact page

3.2 CLASSICA Twitter

Twitter (Figure 14) will primarily be used to create opportunities for two-way dialogue with citizens and other stakeholders and to drive traffic to our website. Our Twitter account³ is linked to the website via a link in the header and by the inclusion of the Twitter feed in the website footer. PT will actively manage the account with all project partners providing input, regularly sharing and tweeting material relevant to the project and promoting project activities. Partners have been encouraged to follow the Twitter account and to tag the project (@classicaproject) in related posts.

Figure 14 CLASSICA on Twitter @classicaproject

3.3 CLASSICA LinkedIn

The CLASSICA LinkedIn group⁴ (Figure 15 below) provides a professional hub for the project team members to share and disseminate project news on LinkedIn. The LinkedIn group can similarly be accessed via a link in the website header.

³ <https://twitter.com/classicaproject>

⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/14085801/>

Figure 15 CLASSICA on LinkedIn – CLASSICA Horizon Europe

4 Impact & Conclusion

This report describes the CLASSICA project website and social media channels which went live in the opening months of the project. D6.1 'Website and Online Communications Setup Report' was developed in line with D6.2 'Communication and Dissemination Plan', which was submitted at the same time. The website will be promoted through social media channels, via press releases attached to the project, and during events where partners present the project mission and results. This ever-growing resource will evolve over the lifetime of the project, delivering clear and relevant project-related information to citizens and specialist audiences.